

UKE kinome abstract

Title: Profiling the kinome in progressive multiple sclerosis

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Objectives

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an immune-mediated, neuroinflammatory disease characterised by demyelination and neurodegeneration. Current disease modifying therapies target the inflammatory component of the disease and have limited effect on progressive disability, which is driven by neurodegeneration. Recently, however, a Bruton's tyrosine kinase inhibitor (tolebrutinib) displayed efficacy in a clinical trial for progressive MS. Despite this, there has been little focus on total kinase activity in MS.

We hypothesise that kinome profiling could inform regarding the pathophysiology of progressive MS and yield new opportunities for targeted treatment. The objective of this study was to map the kinome in progressive MS and determine if kinase activity is associated with clinical measures of disease severity.

Methods

Using PamGene™ technology, the kinome profile was compared in mesenchymal stromal cell (MSC) and peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMC) lysates (n=6), isolated from people with relapsing-remitting MS (RRMS), secondary progressive MS (SPMS) and healthy controls. Total kinase activity was measured using tyrosine kinase (PTK) and serine-threonine (STK) PamChip® arrays on the Pamstation12® with BioNavigator software®.

Results

Total kinase activity was significantly reduced in SPMS PBMCs compared with control and RRMS PBMCs. In MSCs, PTK activity was significantly increased in SPMS compared with control cells and this pattern was reversed for STK activity. SPMS kinase activity was positively

associated with clinical measures of disease progression and severity in both PBMCs and MSCs. Pathway enrichment analysis highlighted specific kinases with roles in immune signalling, oxidative stress, axonal outgrowth, axonal transport and cytoskeletal regulation.

Conclusion

With additional validation and interrogation of the underlying pathways, analysis of the kinome has the potential to identify novel disease biomarkers and therapeutic interventions in progressive MS.

Confirmation

We have demonstrated that the kinome profile is significantly altered in progressive MS with potential implication for the development of biomarkers and novel therapeutics.